

Simulation of the Performance of the Reforming of Methane in a Primary Reformer

A. Alkattib, M. Boumaza

Abstract—Steam reforming is industrially important as it is incorporated in several major chemical processes including the production of ammonia, methanol, hydrogen and ox alcohols. Due to the strongly endothermic nature of the process, a large amount of heat is supplied by fuel burning (commonly natural gas) in the furnace chamber. Reaction conversions, tube catalyst life, energy consumption and CO₂ emission represent the principal factors affecting the performance of this unit and are directly influenced by the high operating temperatures and pressures.

This study presents a simulation of the performance of the reforming of methane in a primary reformer, through a developed empirical relation which enables to investigate the effects of operating parameters such as the pressure, temperature, steam to carbon ratio on the production of hydrogen, as well as the fraction of non converted methane.

It appears from this analysis that the exit temperature T_e , the operating pressure as well the steam to carbon ratio has an important effect on the reforming of methane.

Keywords—Reforming, methane, performance, hydrogen, parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE steam reformer is very important process equipment, used in the production of ammonia, via the production of hydrogen. The reformer is a major consumer of energy [1], [2], [3]) and the efficiency of the reformer section has a major bearing on the overall energy consumption of the plant. However due to the large amount of energy consumption by this unit on one hand, and due to the environment protection (reduction of CO₂ emission) on the other hand, most of the actual research is oriented in finding ways of reducing the energy consumption in the primary reformer, through an increase of methane reaction rates. The optimization of these parameters requires a finite and precise investigation of the catalyst tube including process and conversion parameters [4], [5].

The present paper presents various profiles of the percentage of hydrogen and unconverted methane with respect several to process parameters such as the temperatures, operating pressures, and steam flow rates, during the steam reforming of methane.

II. PRIMARY REFORMER DESCRIPTION

The primary reformer is basically a furnace containing burners and tubes packed with supported nickel catalyst.

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Ammonia is synthesized by chemically combining hydrogen and nitrogen under pressure, in the presence of a catalyst. The Hydrogen requirement is met by, catalytically reacting a mixture of steam and hydrocarbons, usually methane at an elevated temperature to form a mixture of Hydrogen and oxides of Carbon.

Gas leaving the primary reformer contains a small fraction of methane as well as Hydrogen H₂, Nitrogen N₂, carbon monoxide CO, carbon dioxide CO₂, water vapor H₂O and inert gases (argon). This gas mixture flows to the secondary reformer reaction (A) is endothermic and proceeds at high temperatures (800 to 900°C). A high ratio of steam to hydrocarbon (Z) and a low pressure generally produce higher rate of hydrogen and carbon monoxide [6], [7].

III. PRIMARY REFORMER MODELING

A. Introduction

There exists two distinct sections in the primary reformer, the radiant zone and the convective zone. Therefore the modeling must consider both sections. The radiant zone represents the section where methane is converted to carbon monoxide and hydrogen inside the catalyst tube. The convective zone is used to collect the heat from the exhaust gas leaving the radiant zone.

In order to investigate the effects of operating parameters on the unconverted methane in the reformer, it is necessary to simulate the catalytic tube primary reformer [9]-[11]. The simulation is based on energy, mass and momentum balances along the tube.

In order to investigate the effects of operating parameters on the production of hydrogen, it is necessary to simulate the catalytic tube primary reformer. The simulation is based on mass, energy and momentum balances through the tube..

The simulation is based on the following assumptions;

- It is assumed that all the tubes are similar in the primary reformer, and therefore one tube can represent all the tubes...
- It is supposed that physical properties of the gas remain constant in the radial direction
- The fluid is considered to be a mixture of chemical species. And the composition changes as the reaction proceeds.

Fig. 1 Primary reformer catalytic tube

B. Energy Balance

The heat of reaction at temperature T is calculated as follows [5]:

$$\Delta H_T = \Delta H_{298}^0 + \sum_j \left(\int_{298}^T C_{p_j} \cdot dT \right)_{\text{prods}} - \sum_i \left(\int_{298}^T C_{p_j} \cdot dT \right)_{\text{reacts}} \quad (1)$$

As the mixture undergoes a chemical reaction, then the enthalpy of component 'i' is given by [12]:

$$\hat{h}_{fi} = \Delta \hat{h}_{fi}^0 + \int_{T_0}^T C_{p_i} \cdot dT \quad (2)$$

\hat{h}_{fi}^0 : Standard heat of formation of component 'i'.

Standard heat of formations as well as specific heats of different fluids is available in the literature [15].

C. Mass Balance

Applying principles of mass conservation [8]

$$\frac{dm_{i,tot}}{dt} = \rho_1 \cdot v_1 \cdot S_1 - \rho_2 \cdot v_2 \cdot S_2 + m_{i,m} + R_{i,tot} \quad (3)$$

$R_{i,tot}$: Rate of reaction of 'i'

$m_{i,tot}$: Total mass of component 'i' within the reformer boundaries.

ρ_i : Density of component 'i'

Equation (3) can be arranged as follows;

$$\frac{dm_{i,tot}}{dt} = -\Delta m_i + m_{i,m} + R_{i,tot} \quad (4)$$

D. Equilibrium Constants, K.

The equilibrium constant is defined as follows [13], [14]:

$$K(T) = \pi_i a_{i,eq}^{v_i} \quad (5)$$

v_i : stoichiometric coefficient

a_i : component activity coefficient.

Thus for the present reactions, the equilibrium constants can be determined as follows;

$$K_{PCH_4} = \frac{P_{CO} \cdot (P_{H_2})^3}{P_{CH_4} \cdot P_{H_2O}} \quad (6)$$

The constant K_{PCH_4} depends on temperatures, and can be calculated through the following relations [16], [17]:

$$K_{PCH_4} = 1.198 \cdot 10^{13} \exp\left(\frac{-26830}{T_s}\right) \quad (7)$$

An empirical correlation has been developed based on the least method square method to determine the effects of operating parameters such as the temperature, the pressure and the steam to carbon ratio on the percentage of unconverted methane (X_{CH_4}) in the primary reformer reaction.

$$\Delta \dot{m}_{CH_4} = (-r_{CH_4} \cdot A \cdot \rho_{cat}) \Delta Z \quad (8)$$

$$X_{CH_4} = M_{iCH_4} - \Delta m_{CH_4}$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This paper has investigated the effect of process parameters such steam to carbon ratio (Z), exit gas pressure (P), exit and inlet gas temperatures (T_s , T_e) (Z) on the percentage of unconverted methane (X_{CH_4}), as well as the production of hydrogen in a primary reformer process.

A. Effect of Pressures, P on Hydrogen Production, H_2

Figs. 2 (a)-(c) show the effect of exit gas pressures for various exit gas temperatures T_s and fixed inlet gas temperature ($T_e=520^\circ\text{C}$) as well as 3 different values of Z, respectively equal to values 2, 2.5, 3.6 on the production of Hydrogen. It can be seen that the production of Hydrogen varies inversely proportional with the pressure for all the cases studied, while the amount of Hydrogen produced varies proportionally with the exit temperature and the steam to carbon ration (Z).

B. Effect of (Z) on X_{CH_4} .

Figs. 3 (a)-(c) illustrate the effect of steam to carbon ratio (Z) for three different exit gas pressures (27, 33 and 39 Bars) and different exit temperatures T_s for an inlet gas temperature T_e (520°C) on the quantity of the unconverted fraction of methane, X_{CH_4} .

These figures show that X_{CH_4} varies inversely proportional with Z for any value of P, and also decreases as P increases, while it is proportional to T_s . The shape of this variation can be best represented by an exponential function

$$(X_{CH_4} = aZ^b).$$

C. Effect of Z on H₂

Figs. 4 (a)-(c) show the effect of steam to carbon ratio (Z) for three different exit gas pressures (27, 33 and 39 Bars) and different exit temperatures T_s for an inlet gas temperature T_e(520°C) on the production of hydrogen.

It can be seen from these figures that the amount of H₂ increases by 8.2% for every increase in the steam/carbon ratio (Z) equal to 0.5 at low pressure (27 bar) and high exit Temperature (T_s). This amount is further increased to 12.4% for the same increase in Z (0.5) at low exit Temperature (T_s), for the same pressure (27 Bars).

At higher pressures and higher T_s, the amount of H₂ increases by 9.4% for an increase of 0.5 in S/C ratio. On the other hand, at high pressure and low T_s, the amount of H₂ increases by 12.7% for every 0.5 increase in S/C ratio. This can leads us that increasing Steam/carbon ration at high T_s does not affect the production of H₂ significantly. However, the production of H₂ increase significantly as the exit temperature (T_s) rises from 740 to 900°C at low pressure and high Z.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper enables to determine the effect of the operating parameters on the percentage of unconverted methane as well as the production of hydrogen in an ammonia primary reformer. Thus the present analysis shows that:

- Steam to carbon ratio (Z) is an important factor in the operation of the ammonia primary reformer and on the production of Hydrogen. A higher value of Z will produce higher production rate of Hydrogen, reduces the quantity of methane non converted as well as the formation of carbon which can reduce the efficiency of the catalyst [14], [15].
- Higher exit temperature T_s, reduces the amount of unconverted methane; however, it is recommended to limit this temperature to 900°C in order to avoid the melting of the catalyst, reduce the energy load as well as CO₂ emission.
- The inlet gas mixture temperature T_e does not have a direct impact of the amount of unconverted methane, but affects directly the energy consumed by the reformer.
- The operating pressure has impact on the production of hydrogen at high exit gas temperatures.

NOMENCLATURE

- C_{pi}: Specific heat of component 'i' (J/mole.K)
- H: Specific enthalpy (J/kg)
- m: Mass flow rate (Kg/sec).
- n: molar flow rate (mole/sec)
- R_i: rate of reaction (moles/moles)
- v: Fluid velocity (m/sec)
- P: Fluid pressure (Bar)
- P_i: Partial gas pressure (Bar)
- x: Mole fraction
- T_e: Inlet gas temperature (°C)
- T_s: Outlet gas temperature (°C)
- X_{CH4}: Percentage of unconverted methane

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2 Effect of the pressure on the production of Hydrogen for various exit Temperature and Z (a) Z= 2.1, (b) Z=2.51, (c) Z=3.9

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3 Effect of steam to carbon ratio (Z) on the fraction of unconverted methane (XCH4) for various exit temperatures, Ts and pressure (P) (a) P= 27 bar, (b) P=33 bar, (c) P=39 bar

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4 Effect of steam to carbon ratio (Z) on the production of hydrogen (H₂) for various exit temperatures, Ts and pressure (P) (a) P= 27 bar, (b) P=33 bar, (c) P=39 bar

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